

Significance of Watershed Management with IRBM Approach –from Dulung Basin Perspective, West Bengal, India

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Abstract: In India, watersheds have become the pivotal unit for different rural development programs. India's first guideline for integrated watershed development (1986) highlighted the management of watersheds with impacts on the livelihood system. Watershed management involves the treatment of the land surface, available water, and vegetation for the benefit of farmers, communities, and society. At present, IWRM (Integrated Water Resource Management) is recognized by many countries around the world as a model, the paradigm, for establishing good water governance. Integrated River Basin Management (IRBM) is a part of this perspective. The Present study focuses on watershed management to prepare a resource-based development plan for sustainable development. It involves an integration of resources available in land, water, and plant environment. In some cases, integration among different basins, even among sub-basins is needed to evaluate the dynamics of the water resource. Here lies the importance of the integration of river basins. Dulung, a river with unique nature, portrays a distinctive hydrological perspective in its catchment. Different terrain characters represent unique features that need coordination for management. Within 14 sub-watersheds of the basin, the resource base has been analyzed and it is observed that some areas require effective water governance measures for maintaining livelihood sustenance.

Keywords: *Natural system, Watershed, Integrated development, Livelihood, Water Governance*

I. INTRODUCTION

The concept of watershed management has passed through several phases. In its initial stages, it was a subject of forestry and forestry-related hydrology and had been considered solely an affair of government forest departments. Then, it became land resource management-related activities with an eye on economic benefits. Finally, the focus has shifted to the beneficiaries. It is *The Dublin principles* (1992) where the attention has been given to water as a finite resource and clearly indicated that-, a) water management and development should include stakeholders, b) water is an economic good, c) women play a central role in management and conservation of water. In fact, The Dublin Principles have served as a guide for the global water dialogue. It is now "participatory and integrated" watershed management, with the involvement and contribution of local people. Watershed Management refers to the conservation, regeneration, and judicious uses of all available resources in a watershed. It brings about the best possible balance in the environment using all available resources. The incidents like degradation of the environment have given birth to the idea of regeneration and conservation of nature. It is only possible by promoting awareness among the stakeholders and participation of the people who inhabit the watersheds.

Geographically, a "watershed is an area that supplies water by surface or subsurface flow to a given drainage system or body of water, be it a stream, river, wetland, lake, or ocean (World Bank, 2001)". In another way, the watershed is "that area of land, a bounded hydrologic system, within which all living things are inextricably linked by their common water course and where, as humans settled, simple logic demanded that they become part of a community" (Powell, John Wesley; 1869). River basin is, a larger watershed with an area of more than 10 km². Each watershed being a distinct "hydrological unit", possesses unique set up of rock, soil, landform, and vegetation. As water flows freely across state and political boundaries, it is important to form management plans for entire basins instead of single towns or tributaries. All components of watershed management are interdependent and interactive. This includes community development, soil and land management, water management, crop management, afforestation, pasture or fodder development, and livestock management.

1.1 Integrated River Basin Management Approach

At present, IWRM (Integrated Water Resource Management) is recognized by many countries around the world for establishing good water governance. The key elements to a successful IRBM (Integrated River Basin Management) initiative are the following:

- integration of policies, decisions, and costs among sectors like industry, agriculture, urban development, navigation, fisheries management, and conservation
- formulation of decisions at the river basin scale
- active participation by all relevant stakeholders in transparent planning and decision-making
- adequate investment by governments, private sectors, and civil society organizations for river basin planning and participation processes
- creation of a knowledge bank of the river basin

The Global Water Partnership (GWP), a leading advocate of IWRM, proposes two interrelated approaches: the “*natural system*” approach and the “*human system*” approach for water resource management. The natural system includes the natural resource base and conforms to the natural assets. The human system consists of the human resource base of the basin with a focus on integrating the different groups of people in all sectors and development activities. The coordination between uses and users demands continuous participation by stakeholders to decide how water is allocated, how problems are resolved, and how negotiations can be made. In the river basin, integration of all its sub-basins or watersheds is needed. Here the resource base is meant for the whole basin. Until and unless coordination is made possible the results of the management cannot be perceived. Watershed management approaches need to be adapted to the local situation. The newly emerged concept paves the way for efficient use of rainfall and run-off in rural areas.

1.2 Rural Economy and Watershed Development

In India, where nearly 70% of its people live in villages and agricultural practices play a key role in the livelihood system, attention has been paid to boosting the rural economy in the planning periods. Nearly 60% of India’s arable land is not suitable for large-scale irrigation practices. Different corners of India still lack irrigation facilities, sufficient food, and fodder crops and need an integrated approach for overall improvement. Watershed, a unit with natural boundaries, identification, and its treatment in the process of management has been considered one of the best ways out. River basin management requires integrated land use planning in upland areas and lower reaches of the catchment. Thus, watershed management requires coordination and aims to optimize various land uses with a focus on impacts of hydrology and ecology, and on the people living in it. The approach is participatory in nature, people-friendly, and directed to the problems and needs of rural communities.

1.3 Ethics of Watershed Management

The principle of watershed management lies systematic management of all the precipitation within it. These include:

- to conserve and develop water resources for land resource development
- developmental planning on a watershed basis to conserve the landscape ecology and biodiversity of both the upstream (catchment area) and downstream environment through existing land use practices
- to change in water-sediment-vegetation regime of the watershed
- doing land evaluation in assessing the existing soil-water-vegetation inter-relationship for future planning

So, it is evident that the river basin (a large watershed), a self-defended area, is a basic scientific unit of study. Even experts also believe that the only way to halt the civilizational slide into ecologic disaster is to reorientate our thinking toward “watershed consciousness.” (Brock Dolman, *Basins of Relations: A Citizen’s Guide to Protecting and Restoring Our Watershed*. Occidental, CA, Estados Unidos: Water Institute, 2008).

1.4 Identity of the Study Area

Dulung, a left bank tributary of river Subarnarekha and a fifth-order stream with a basin area of about 1,270 km² (approx), lies between 22°09' N - 22°34' N and 86°39' E - 87°04' E. It is located on the fringe of the Chotonagpur plateau and covers part of the Jhargram district of West Bengal (86.5 %) and part (13.5 %) of the East Singhbhum district of Jharkhand (see Figure: 1). The river originates from a slightly elevated area near Dulungdiha mouza of Ergoda Gram Panchayet, Binpur Block, close to Chakuliya (Jharkhand) and finally joins Subarnarekha near Rohini in West Bengal. During its course, it receives several tributaries that enhance its fluvimetric dimensions. There are 14 sub-basins with varying geographic frameworks in the basin. The sub-basins of upper reaches differ in economic and social perspective from those of the lower reaches. The villages also possess some distinct regional characteristics. Here lies the need for the integration of all 14 watersheds. There are several issues- social, economic, and environmental, related to the sustainability of the basin. All these should be treated in an integrated manner and in a dynamic way to reach the goal.

Figure 1: Location of Dulung River Basin

II. OBJECTIVE

The main objectives of the study are:

1. to analyze the river basin in its resource base.
2. to identify and highlight the developmental inequalities within the subunits of the watershed
3. formulate a best-suited integrated development plan following the IRBM approach for all-round development.

III. METHODOLOGY FOLLOWED

The river basin is identified and demarcated both topographically and cartographically. The required database is constructed by acquiring data both from primary sources (field survey) and secondary sources (Survey of India toposheets, reports, journals, books, gazetteers, maps, satellite images, etc.). The database is managed (storage, editing, manipulation, and analysis) and has been mapped and modeled primarily with the help of Geographic Information System software. General cartographic principles have been followed for representing the output of the analysis.

The methodology includes the following steps:

- i) basin area has been delineated from the survey of India toposheets nos.73 J/10, 73 J/14, 73 J/15, 73 N/3, 73 N/4
- ii) Block maps are collected from the respective block offices of the districts of Jhargram and East or Purbi Singbhum district
- iii) Gram Panchayats are considered a unit of study
- iv) delineated basin areas are overlaid on the Gram Panchayat
- v) database has been prepared from the West Bengal district census handbook and respective block offices
- vi) regarding techniques of mapping and diagram, general principles and GIS have been followed.
- vii) thematic maps with proportional symbols and choropleth have been prepared with MapInfo version 8.5, TNT MIPs, and other software.

IV. DISCUSSION

4.1 The Resource Base

4.1.1 Water resource

The physical aspects of the watershed area are not so varied in character, except for the source region. It is margined by several *pahars* (local names, meaning hills) in the northwest corner like *Kanaisore* (370 m), *Choukisoile* (320 m), and some unnamed small hills. The adjacent contours with more than 200 m contours and closer spacing indicate a relatively steep slope (10°) in the northwest part. The alignment of the contours and stream flow clearly indicate that the region slope down from north-northwest to south-southeast (see Figure: 2). At source it is named *Dulung Nala* that starts the journey from *Choukisoile pahar* ($22^\circ 37'N$, $86^\circ 41'E$) of Belpahari of West Bengal. Some small streamlets reach the plains and form a distinct flow. Several streams join the Dulung and enhance its total discharge. *Kupan nala*, *Deb nala*, and *Palpala khal* are the main right bank tributaries while *Simana* and *Champa khal* join from the left. Some large-scale gullies are associated with the middle parts of the river over the rolling plains. The area at the confluence is associated with 30 m elevation and less. Forming a hook bend it ultimately joins Subarnarekha River south of Rohini, Sankrail block, Jhargram, West Bengal.

Figure 2: Natural System of the Dulung watershed (available water sources)

a) Contours and streams b) Slopes (Wentworth's method)

Water resources include:

i) *Water through streams* - Run-off usually makes its way to stream channels as surface or subsurface flow. The peak run-off rate and run-off volume are of great importance in the planning and design of soil conservation works. The general climate with its temperature, rainfall, and relative humidity also plays a significant role (see Figure: 3).

Figure 3: Rainfall- temperature- humidity conditions

In the study, the main sources of run-off are *Kupan nala* and *Dulung nala* flowing eastward for 8.53 km and southwards for 12.80 km respectively. The two then join at Dhadka to flow eastwards and meet with *Simana khal*. Then, the river flows as fifth order southwards and south-eastward for about 70.51 km, till it joins the Subarnarekha.

For the measurement of run-off, the outlet of the stream has been modified into a prismatic section. A stream gauge, which can read up to 2m, was installed at several outlets. The depth of flow through the outlet was measured thrice a day, at 8:00 a.m., 1:00 p.m., and 5:00 p.m. The run-off from the stream has been measured by the velocity area method. Run-off was determined by multiplying the cross-sectional area of the stream by the average velocity of the flow of the stream.

That is, $Q = AV$, Where, Q = Discharge through the outlet (m^3/s), A = Area of cross-section of flow (m^2) V = Average velocity of flow (m/s). Therefore, the discharge from the watershed is 801, 329,760 m^3 (see Figure 4).

Estimation of WATER BALANCE:

Total Basin Area: 1270 km^2 . Annual Average Rainfall: 1305.08 mm,

40 % of the total rainfall loss is due to evaporation and transpiration.

40 % of 1305.08 mm = 522.032 mm

60 % of 1305.08 mm = 783.048 mm

Total available volume of water in the basin = 1270 sq km. x 783.048 mm
 = 1270 000000 sq m x 0.783048 m
 = 9,94,470,960 m^3

Water reaches the surface = 9,94,470,960 m^3

Amount of water available on the Surface (runoff + storage) = 9,94,470,960 m^3

Discharge = Cross-sectional area x Velocity

Here the cross-sectional area = width of the river x depth

= 55 m x 2.1 m

= 115.5 sq m

Discharge = 115.5 sq m x 0.22 m /sec

= 25.41 m^3 /sec.

Total Discharge as flow = 25.41 m^3 x 365 days

= 25.41 m^3 x 31536000 sec (as 1 day = 86400 sec)

= 801,329,760 m^3

CONSUMPTION

Human consumption = 325492 x 20 lt x 365 days = 2,376,091,600 liters = 2,376,091.6 m^3

Animal consumption = 526179 x 35 lt. x 365 days = 6,721,936,725 liters = 6,721,936.725 m^3

Water use in Irrigation = 38479000 sq m x 0.5m = 19,239,500 m^3

Total consumption = 28,337,528.33 m^3

Water storage on surface = 9,94,470,960 m^3 (A)

Total expenditure due to consumption = 28,337,528.33 m^3 (B)

Total Discharge as flow = 8,01,329,760 m^3 (C)

Available amount = A - (B + C) = 164,803,671.67 m^3 .

Therefore, there is a water surplus situation in the Basin.

Figure 4: Estimation of Water Balance in Dulung Basin [Data collected during field survey; measures are standard in tropical countries]

ii) Surface water - ponds and water bodies

In earlier periods, well-maintained farm ponds act as good natural storage for surface water and supplied water for irrigation and even for domestic purposes. In fact, ponds help to maintain the water table of the area within safe limits. In some places, the ponds are transformed into marshy lands, and agricultural plots. There are so many ponds, *bandhs*, *jhils* in the basin which cover approximately 8 km^2 (7,935,000 m^2 as computed by the author). Most of the ponds and water bodies especially those in the upper reaches dry up in the sultry heat of summer (see Table 1). But the post-monsoon period experiences a full-to-the-brim situation. Monsoon and post-monsoon periods enjoy a high-water level which goes down below 9m in the lean period. These water bodies supply water for domestic purposes and irrigation in some cases. They also act as local groundwater recharge zone. In the uplands (above 100m), therefore, it is proposed to take up soil and moisture conservation measures. In lowlands, water harvesting tanks, and in the upper catchment areas check dams are the best option for moisture conservation.

Table1: Details of major water bodies in the Basin
(Information collected during fieldwork, 2021)

iii) Groundwater

The main source of the extraction of groundwater is open dug wells. Tube wells are also in use. Water level fluctuations are common in the pre-monsoon and post-monsoon periods. Most of the wells are dried up for two to three months during summer. Groundwater in many places is used for domestic, agricultural, and irrigation purposes. A maximum number of inhabitants depend on dug wells for drinking water. The depth of water in open wells in the area ranges from 5 to 10 m. In summer, most of them become get dried up due to the lowering of groundwater level. However, in the post-monsoon period, the water level goes up. The water level lies within 3 m

Sl. No.	Name/adjacent to villages	Location (North /East)	Area (m ²)	Present status
1	Jarda	22.58, 86.76	74660	earthen weir on one side (4m)
2	Giridhar bandh (near Silda)	22.61, 86.81	120700	protected by 2 sides with earthwork
3	Parihati bandh	22.52, 86.85	123700	water depth 2m or more
4	Haludbani	22.49, 86.88	100700	<i>nayanjuli</i> of the southeastern railway line
5	Gidhni	22.49, 86.85	62800	protected by earthwork
6	Palpala Bandh	22.43, 86.81	310300	earthen check dam with sluice gate on Palpala <i>khal</i>
7	Bhanga band	22.40, 86.82	138900	earth weir on one side
8	Bandhdihi	22.40, 86.75	106400	not maintained properly
9	Bhalukkhulya	22.38, 86.75	161300	5 m weir on one side
10	Barbera	22.37, 86.79	614900	4 m weir dam using local slope
11	Bauria bandh	22. 35, 86.86	876200	protected by earthwork of 4 m elevation
12	Choto Sirsi	22.30, 87.07	33400	domestic use on a 1 st order stream

from the surface. Tube wells serve people in many villages specifically where the water level is much lower. The depth of tube wells ranges from 20 to 35 m (see Figure 5). The people harness the groundwater potential for growing *rabi* crops to boost agriculture production. Submersible pump sets explore the water from the ground at a much greater depth, sometimes more than 50 feet. Available surface water and a very sleek flow of river water through channels, force the villagers to rely on the extraction of groundwater. In some villages, as surveyed, shallow tube well is the only alternative for drinking water both for human being and livestock, bathing, and performing daily chores.

iv) Irrigation canal

Some canals of shorter length from Koala and Ghumna *nala* crosses over the area to meet the need the irrigation. Therefore, Kharbandhi, Petbindhi, Rogra, and Rohini gram Panchayats can practice multiple cropping throughout the year. As the water availability is not certain in all the seasons the construction of canals for irrigation may not seem to be feasible and economic also. Here, the construction of small check dams, and rainwater harvesting structures may serve the purpose of recharging the water table.

Figure 5: Ground Water level of the watersheds

4.1.2 Land Resource

Land, being the base for all production, is considered an important resource with variable characteristics. Land use pattern across the area shows that the nested basin possesses the largest geographic area (279.35 km²) followed by *Dulung Nala* (151.45 km²) and the smallest sub-basin is *Ghumna khal* subbasin (31.48 km²). Nested Basin is the area of alluvium deposits and the area records the largest share (nearly 65 % of its total area) of net cropped area, the smallest being the *Deb Nala* subbasin. As it possesses the maximum share of forest area, it has very little area for cultivation (see Figure 6). The area under wasteland is largest in *Dulung Nala* followed by *Kupan nala*, the smallest being observed again in Nested Basin indicating its land capability in soil character and its fertility status.

Figure 6: Categories of land in various uses in different sub-basins

Land use near streams is largely influenced by riparian conditions and there are more options available for different economic pursuits. The satellite images and the land use and land cover map also help to identify the dominant sector within or adjacent to the riparian area along each river and stream (see Figure 7). The Land coverage map portrays a better understanding of the dynamics of the basin. Agricultural crops cover the field for part of the year while at other times the field is open. Crop rotation pattern, crop type, and total acreage in crops vary by year.

Figure 7: Map showing the uses and coverage of the land
(Source: <https://www.landsat.org>)

4.1.3 Forest Resource

Forest act as a “safety net” to the surrounding households who are entirely dependent on this natural resource (Sunderlin et al., 2005). Dulung Basin comprises parts of the *Jhargram Forest division* and part of the *Singbhum Forest* of Jharkhand. Physiographically, the upper catchment area is part of the Dalma Forest Range. The middle reaches comprise *dense sal*, *open sal*, and *dense mixed jungle mainly sal*. Though forests are absent in the lower reaches some *jungles* are observed. Typical moist deciduous is the characteristic vegetation. Hundreds of floras, shrubs, herbs, and weeds enrich the forest to a large extent. The fauna also represents a varied character. The timber species include *Sal*, *Piasal*, *Kend*, *Mahul*, *Kusum*, *Karam*, *Asan*, *Bahera*, and so on.

The river basin area consists of nearly 30 % scheduled tribes, and 18 % scheduled castes population. This large number of tribal people live in harmony with nature and are fully dependent on the forest and its products for their day-to-day needs. Uses of small plants as food items or vegetables are very common among different communities. Some of the nontimber forest products like *kham alu* are rich in nutrients and valued for medicinal properties. Wild edible plants are one of the prime sources of livelihood for rural communities. Various plant parts like fruit, leaf, flower, tuber, rhizomes, roots, and seeds are sources of food for the residents of the study area. Villagers have taken the forest landscape as an important resource and show a great reliance on the forest produce. The tribes sell *sal* leaves, *bidi* leaves, fuel wood, and *dhup* (resin) in the local market and at quite well-off villages nearby. In the lean period (non-paddy season) they go to the forest and collect firewood to sell to small shops or local *huts* (markets).

Livestock population

Open grazing in forest land is the conventional rearing practice for forest fringe communities. Livestock includes *deshi* cattle, goats, sheep, and buffalo. Piggery is a general phenomenon in the villages of Chakulia, Baharagora, Gopiballavpur II, and Binpur II which are dominated by the tribes. This ownership of livestock complements the rice-based cropping system on one hand; on the other, it increases the dependency on forests.

Tourism Activities

The red lateritic soil, and lush green *sal* forests create great attractions for tourists from different parts of West Bengal. Surrounding Jhargram town, many tourist destinations have sprung up with forest landscapes. This special quality added extra advantage to the people as it creates temporary employment opportunities for the locals. Eco-tourism centers have been developed at Hatibari, Jhargram, Jhilli, Kendua, and Bandarvulla (eco hut) areas amidst the serene and green surroundings.

4.2 Livelihood System and the Issues in the Watershed

Within the sub-basins, the natural and human resource base has been analyzed and some areas have more effective opportunities compared to others. The nonworker category is maximum in all sub-basins (see Figure: 8). Though it includes the age group from 14 to 65 years, and considers the house makers, aged, and children, this share must be reduced to achieve the goal of development. Disparities were also noticed among the share of wasteland, nonworker categories, and marginal workers (see Figure 9).

Figure 8. Working Status in the Sub Basins

The livelihood system, now, has a part of a supply-driven and top-down approach. The analysis clearly indicates that the rural people really pass with many disadvantages in natural, physical, economic, and social hindrances. Regarding water availability, there is a surplus situation, but in terms of accessibility, there is a problem. The sources of water in different subbasins are not lacking as the study reflects and the water balance study of the basin calculated. The real problem lies with preserving the water and its effective use. Flooding, is a common phenomenon in years of heavy monsoon in the lower reaches. Again, drought conditions also have been noticed in the year of deficit rainfall. Thus, the basin is affected by the hands of nature.

Figure 9. Distribution of wasteland and nonworkers

Imbalance in development occurs due to disparities in physical, hydrological, and economic parameters in different watersheds. The combination index value which is the aggregate rank score of some parameters, indicates a comparatively better picture in the central area and the lower reaches of the basin (see figure:10). There are 16 panchayats with less than 20 scores meaning a better position in all aspects of development. All this area coincides with a good physical resource base of the alluvial plains.

Figure 10: Development Index at Panchayet level

The areas with a high score, more than 40 are recorded at Bhalukbindha, Bend, and Lodhasuli panchayats which coincide with the source area of the river with rough terrain. Badrikanpur, Baingla, Kamarigora, Balibandh panchayats of Chakulia block and Rupuskundi, Gondanata, and Baramara areas of Baharagora block represent a disheartening picture. All these analyses clearly hint

at the direction of effective management practices in the whole basin area. So, the management perspective must view the problems of the basin in a systematic way. The problems can only be solved by considering different measures to keep parity with the problems of the watershed

Table 2: Identification of problems, analysis, and proposal for interventions

Sl. No.	Problems	Major issues	Interventions required
1	soil erosion (soil loss, slope failure, loss of fertility)	slope moderate to gentle, gully erosion, presence of acidic soil	gully plugging and construction of small check dams by boulders
2	Water conservation (groundwater table)	water table low, slope moderate to low, less water percolation	building of water harvesting structures, check dams, river lift irrigation
3	Crop coverage	only 20% of the area	conversion of wasteland into productive land, introduction of horticulture
4	Agriculture productivity (low compared)	Low average productivity, monocropping of paddy	Implementation of crop diversification, adoption of HYV seeds, and proper land use planning.
5	Livestock productivity (yield of milk, meat, eggs)	cattle, goats of indigenous type, used for milk and cultivation, while goats for meat only.	proper vaccination, cross-breeding of live stocks, providing grazing land for the fodder crops
6	A perusal of livelihood activities for landless	low wage rate, implementation of MGNREGA (fewer man-days)	formation of SHGs, execution of MGNREGA, vocational training
7	Participation of beneficiaries	lack of awareness regarding watershed development	involvement of SHGs in increasing awareness.

Abbreviation: SHGs-Self Help Group, HYV- High Yielding Variety, MGNREGA- Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act.

4.3 The need for the basin in terms of management

The existing livelihood support system clearly shows that it needs a take-off to change the whole situation. Only proper management practices according to the guideline, laid down by the IRBM approach, may give a boost to its developmental initiatives. The needs of the basin in terms of management are:

4.3.1 Conversion of Wasteland for effective uses

According to Bhumbala and Khare, *wastelands* are ecologically unstable lands whose topsoil has been completely lost and which have developed toxicity in root zones that hampers the growth of most plants, both annual crops and trees. In the Dulung basin, there are various types of wastelands (gullies, uplands with or without scrub, degraded forest, degraded pastures, barren rocky surfaces) kept unutilized. Land and water degradation are silent but pose a growing menace. This is causing rural displacement, changes in land use, migration to cities, and empowerment of the population. National Land Use and Wastelands Development Council and National Wasteland Development Board have adopted different measures to change the scenario. Planting and sowing of multipurpose trees, shrubs, grasses, legumes, and pasture land development may be proved fruitful at this. The wasteland situation at different sub-basins in connection with the marginal and nonworker categories reflects that in some cases marginal worker % is higher and the nonworker category surpasses all this (see Figure 10). It explains that if wasteland can be converted into productive use the share of the nonworking class may be changed. This may increase the livelihood options and overall income of the people concerned.

4.3.2 Crop diversification

Cultivation of paddy and crop diversification in rain-fed uplands require rainwater management, off-season plowing, early sowing and weeding, timely fertilizer application, early harvesting, and proper soil intercultural practices. Deep-rooted crops like maize, black gram, pigeon pea, cowpea, groundnut and so on may change the procedure of crop diversification. Growing vegetables in the paddy field between two cropping seasons (see Plate: 4) may change the situation. There must be an emphasis on integrated weed management, nutrient management, rainwater management, and the adoption of plant protection measures.

4.3.3 Livestock Development and regeneration of fodder and fuel

Livestock activities give good returns to the people, especially during off-seasons when they do not have employment. There is good scope for financing these activities under Swarna Jayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojana which provides marketing networks or cooperatives. Poultry farmers may be encouraged to take up the construction of hatchery units. Farmers could be encouraged to take up feed mixing units for poultry farms. The increase in forest area in the sub-basin shows that there is an increase in livestock population, which means there is a positive correlation (see Figure 11). Forests and surroundings pastures lands are good places for grazing. At the same time, inhabitants fond of staying near the forest, choose to keep pigs and goats in houses for earning income in parts of the year.

Figure 11: Correlation between forest area and livestock population

4.3.4 Rise in groundwater levels

Groundwater level varies in the basin in the summer and winter months. The Presence of sufficient rainwater harvesting structures like check dams may be fruitful in keeping the surface soil recharged. Two such important structures are effective in the subbasins.

- Auligaria project on Champa *khal* where a dam has been constructed (see Figure 12),
- Checkdam on Palpala *khal* creates a large storage reservoir that supplies irrigation water in a dry period and raises the groundwater level (see Figure 13).

Figure 13: Water bodies and dam on Palpala *khal*

Like these structures, many more such structures are needed. Presently pond excavation has been done under MGNREGS (Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme), and storage tanks are also created, but not in sufficient numbers. Moreover, the use of shallow tube wells for rabi crops further worsens the situation. Raising of water level is only possible by the formation of more check dams at different places of varying slopes.

4.3.5 Horticulture practices

Consequent upon the success of the *wadi* (meaning horticulture garden in Gujarati) approach in Gujarat in providing horticulture-based sustainable livelihood for the tribals, National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development took initiatives to initiate the model in West Bengal and sanctioned two Development Projects in Ranibandh and Bundwan blocks in Bankura and Purulia districts respectively. In the same way, cashew nut is an important horticultural crop grown in the basin (see plate 5). The main areas of cashew production are in the blocks of Baharagora, Jhargram, Binpur II, Gopiballavpur II, and Sankrail. Following the principles of the National Horticulture Mission, some success has been attained. Various components under the plan are - the development of plantation infrastructure and increased land coverage under horticulture crops through micro irrigation practices. Turmeric, ginger, and tuber crops can be good options in the basin. Floriculture of marigold, jasmine, rose, tube rose and so on should be increased. Fruits like mango, guava, and banana may help a lot to bring livelihood security if done on a commercial basis. However, the farmers' response is stated to be abysmal due to high initial investment and small land holdings.

4.3.6 Solving the Problems of marketing agricultural products

One of the major problems of the basin is in marketing agricultural products on a commercial basis. The most population who makes their living depending on agriculture are small and marginal farmers, and sharecroppers. Together they account for more than 50 % percent of all farming households. Financial support from the Government, cooperatives, or banks is not adequate. Giving credit to farmers may become an important step in Marketing. Most large farmers give priority to a rice-based cropping system thinking mainly about food security. Still, this practice does not support the high-income generation. A maximum of the price is shared by the intermediaries. This can only be improved if the marketing channel is controlled more by growers than by middlemen.

4.3.7 Development of tourism activities

Dulung basin with its picturesque landscape provides good potentiality for tourism. The entire area is the paradise of nature lovers with bountiful forests of *sal*, *mahul*, *piyal*, and the sacredness of nature. The melodious folk songs, heritage temples, royal palaces, and wild rhythms of tribal music make the area a more attractive destination for tourists. It is a place where tourists can feel themselves amidst lush green surroundings. The contiguous areas provide ideal destination points for spending a few days with serene beauty and tranquility. Destinations places include Chilkigarh Raj Palace, Kanak Durga Temple, Alampur, Kendua, Jhargram Raj Palace, Deer Park (Jhargram mini zoo), Ghagra Falls, Khandarani lake, Tarafeni Barrage, Belpahari, Rameswar, Topoban, etc (see Figure 14). Visitors from outside throng to various places which provide an opportunity for employment generation. Good

network accessibility is a lacuna here. If these situations are tried out, the area may be considered a good destination point for tourists providing good employment opportunities to its people.

Figure 14: Proposed and existing places of Destinations for tourists

4.3.8 Income-generating activities through SHGs

Livelihoods-enhancing activities in agriculture, fisheries, forestry (collection of non-timber forest products), livestock and household diary, and microenterprises are helpful enough for building skills for the job market. The concept of contract farming, though new, maybe a good way out in agriculture. This provides good scope for captive production of raw materials (fruits and vegetables) catering to the specific needs of users. Fishing on a commercial basis, though prevalent on a small scale, needs more attention. Handicraft and cottage industries may play a good role in making the livelihood support system more fruitful. Some of the villages have fame regarding expertise in potteries, bamboo product making, etc. Small-scale food processing units pave the way for using horticulture products.

Self Help Groups have received the benefits from government programs like Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme and thus improving access to social safety nets and other entitlements for vulnerability reduction of the poorest households. To provide the necessary support for marketing the products at the local, block, and district level, marketing outlets (*haats*) should be developed. In fact, initiatives for setting up small-scale units of cottage industries may be able to make the people of the area self-employed. West Bengal State Rural Livelihood Mission plans to improve the image of *Aajeevika* and *Anandadhara* and help in the sale of produce to the locals. Convergence with other government schemes and programs may be an effective way to ensure higher access to wage employment.

4.4 Constraints to IRBM approach in the watershed

Dulung watershed, from a rural perspective, experience poverty in some hotspot areas. As agriculture is the mainstay and it depends on several factors, the occurrence of poverty is common in the area. Water-related issues and vulnerability have been observed in-1. *standard of living*, 2. *access to water* 3, *biophysical vulnerability*, 4. *water-related hazards*. People living on marginal land are exposed to water-related hazards. The constraints of the watershed area include dependency on rain-fed agriculture and it is a key factor for the high prevalence of rural poverty. Poverty is again aggravated by less water access, especially in cultivated fields. Loss of livelihoods also occurs because of high exposure to water-related hazards.

V CONCLUSION

Dulung Basin, when treated as a watershed, for development purposes, reveals an interesting fact that many things must be done for the benefit of the region. The rain-fed agro-system is characterized by erratic rainfall, land degradation, flooding, and low rainwater use. The water of river Dulung is used for irrigation, drinking, and industrial purposes (brick making). However, *accessibility* of water is not uniform in different geographic settings and *availability* is not sufficient to perform agriculture all year round. Water-related poverty occurs because people either do not have access to water resources or lack in capacity to use them. Agriculture, being the main function, needs much focus so that multiple cropping systems can be developed. Irrigation facilities need to be improved by forming more water harvesting structures. The percentage of main workers, if increased, may change the social and economic situation. The collection of Non-Timber Forest Products plays a significant role in influencing the occupational calendar of the villagers. Reserved and protected *sal* forests of different types really act as important natural assets. Bore wells installation may improve water requirements for domestic use. Encouragement must be given for the shift in cropping patterns such as the cultivation of *pulses-paddy-vegetables* (May--April crop calendar). It may open new livelihood fortuity. The livelihood system will be sustainable when it can cope with, and recover from stress and shocks (drought, flood, etc.) and enhance its capabilities using all kinds of assets. The IWRM framework, as developed by the Global Water Partnership like economic efficiency in water use, equity (Social), and environmental and ecological sustainability, if followed, the river basin may achieve the optimum result soon.

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Appendix

Plate 1: Open space on gravelly red soil in Ergoda Panchayat of Binpur I

Plate 2: Gully erosion near Dahijuri village

Plate 3: Barren rock surface near Bhalkapahari,

Plate 4: Bitter gourd cultivation in the Paddy field at Simli, with a good harvest in Early May'2020

Plate 5: Cashew plants on private land at Simli and the owner with the fruits and seeds (nuts)